

The Influence of Product Quality and Promotion on Revisit Decisions Mediated by Outpatient Satisfaction at St Elisabeth Hospital Bekasi

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ABSTRACT: This study investigates the influence of product quality and promotion on outpatient revisit decisions, with patient satisfaction serving as a mediating variable, at St. Elisabeth Hospital in Bekasi. Employing a quantitative research approach, data were analyzed using the Partial Least Squares - Structural Equation Modeling (PLS-SEM) technique. A total of 160 respondents were selected through purposive sampling. The findings reveal that both product quality and promotion exert a positive and significant impact on patient satisfaction and revisit decisions. Furthermore, patient satisfaction significantly mediates the relationship between product quality and promotion on the decision to revisit. These results highlight the critical role of delivering high-quality healthcare services and implementing effective promotional strategies to foster patient satisfaction and loyalty. The study provides practical implications for hospital management in formulating marketing strategies and enhancing service delivery to sustain and increase patient visit.

KEYWORDS: Product Quality, Promotion, Patient Satisfaction, Revisit Decision

I. INTRODUCTION

Patient repeat visits are very important in the context of health services. Viewed from the perspective of hospital service quality standards according to the hospital accreditation commission (KARS), there are various aspects to ensure that hospitals provide safe, effective, and quality health services. From a business perspective, patient repeat visits are important to maintain the existence of the hospital itself. Where patient interest in repeat visits is influenced by the quality of service provided by the hospital. Patients will stay with a hospital if they are satisfied with the product. Therefore, according to Tjiptono (2016), patient satisfaction must also be accompanied by patient loyalty. Haryanto et al. (2019) explains that there are five actions taken by patients if they are loyal, one of which is making purchases/repeat visits or at least 2 purchases/visits.

Patient satisfaction is one of the indicators in assessing whether the service provided is in accordance with patient expectations. If the quality of service of a hospital provided through the services of doctors provided is optimal, then the patient will feel satisfied (Al-Damen, 2017). Consumers who feel satisfied will make repeat purchases, become loyal to a product or service, and then recommend it to others. This revisit and recommend action will increase patient visits and increase hospital profits (Richter & Muhlestein, 2017).

Research on product marketing mix and promotion is an important topic in marketing studies, because both contribute significantly to the success of a product. According to Paradilla & Janna (2022) in his research found that the marketing mix, patient experience through satisfaction has a significant effect on patient loyalty at Stella Maris Hospital Makasar where the better the product quality, price advantage (competitive price, location advantage and attractive promotions carried out, the higher the patient satisfaction with the services offered.

Table 1. Number of Outpatient Visits in 2021-2023

No.	Year	Information		Total
		Patient New	Patient Long	
1	2021	11989	41758	53747
2	2022	12217	49619	61836
3	2023	14542	56892	71434

Source: Data from St. Elisabeth Hospital Bekasi

Figure 1. Number of JKN and Non-JKN Outpatient Visits

Source: Data from St. Elisabeth Hospital Bekasi

The total number of outpatient visits from 2021-2023 at St. Elisabeth Hospital Bekasi has increased. Based on the data on visits by old patients which have decreased, it shows that patient visits are still relatively low and have not achieved significant progressiveness in the number of new visits and repeat visits. In terms of patient guarantees that have an impact on hospital income, the table above shows data that in 2021 the number of non-JKN outpatient patients at St. Elisabeth Hospital Bekasi was 20,127 patients or around 37% of the total patient visits. In 2022, although overall patient visits increased, the non-JKN patient group decreased by 33% to 20,384. Furthermore, in 2023 the number of non-JKN patients decreased again to 26%, namely 18,992 patients from a total of 71,343 patients.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Patient Satisfaction

The intention to revisit healthcare services is largely influenced by the level of satisfaction experienced during a prior visit. As noted by Richter & Muhlestein (2017), there is a strong positive correlation between patient satisfaction and patient loyalty within the healthcare industry. Their study emphasizes that positive patient experiences contribute significantly to increased hospital profitability, whereas negative experiences are associated with financial losses. Specifically, a positive healthcare experience encourages patients to return for future visits, while a negative experience may lead patients to seek alternative healthcare providers, even those located at a greater distance from their residence. Revisit intention as an individual's desire to return to a particular place within a specified time frame, including their willingness to make frequent return visits. This behavioral intention is a reflection of a person's mental state, which indicates a plan or commitment to perform certain actions within a given period. In the context of hospital services, revisit intention is a key indicator of patient loyalty and is directly influenced by the quality of care and overall patient satisfaction.

Patient Satisfaction

According to Tjiptono (2016), satisfaction is a post-purchase evaluation in which the chosen alternative meets or exceeds customer expectations. Conversely, dissatisfaction arises when the perceived outcomes fall short of these expectations. In the context of healthcare services, satisfaction is operationally influenced by the alignment between patient perceptions and expectations. Patients assess hospital service quality based on three primary dimensions: outcomes, processes, and the physical environment. When these elements align with patient needs and expectations, the services are perceived as satisfactory (Sulistyo & Gumilar, 2019). Patient satisfaction reflects not only the perceived value of healthcare services but also their overall effectiveness (Asnawi et al., 2019). It can be defined as the emotional response of patients either satisfaction or dissatisfaction based on their experiences during healthcare service delivery, particularly in terms of how well the service process meets their expectations. Several factors contribute to the perception of healthcare quality, including the promptness of solutions to health concerns, the empathy and professionalism of medical staff, and the clarity and adequacy of the information provided. Therefore, improving patient satisfaction involves not only enhancing medical facilities but also ensuring that healthcare services meet or exceed patient expectations in both clinical and interpersonal aspects.

Product Quality

Products are defined as goods or services evaluated by customers as potential solutions to fulfill their needs (Yuliantine & Siyoto, 2018). In the healthcare sector, the services provided by hospitals function as products that must deliver value and meet patient expectations. According to Tjiptono (2016), quality is the aggregate of features and characteristics of a product or service that determines its ability to satisfy stated or implied needs. In the context of healthcare services, Abassi-Moghaddam et al. (2019) propose a dual-dimensional framework for quality, consisting of technical (clinical) quality and functional (non-clinical) quality. Technical quality refers to the professional competence of healthcare providers, including procedural accuracy, diagnostic precision, and adherence to clinical standards. Functional quality, by contrast, relates to the manner in which healthcare services are delivered. This includes communication, responsiveness, empathy, and the overall interaction between patients and healthcare personnel. Both dimensions are essential in shaping the overall perception of service quality and play a critical role in influencing patient satisfaction and their intention to return.

Promotion

A common misconception is that marketing is solely about selling products or services and engaging in advertising. However, these activities represent only the final stage of a broader marketing process. In contemporary marketing theory, the focus has shifted from a transactional approach to a more relational and customer-oriented perspective. Marketing today is better understood as the process of identifying, understanding, and satisfying customer needs and desires in a sustainable and strategic manner. Promotion, as a component of the marketing mix, plays a critical role in influencing consumer behavior. Elliot et al. (2021) describe promotion as a short-term activity designed to stimulate consumer purchases or encourage intermediaries such as retailers to stock and sell specific products. According to McCarthy, promotion functions as a communication tool that informs, persuades, and reminds consumers about a product or service, with the goal of influencing their purchasing decisions. In the healthcare context, effective promotional strategies are essential for bridging the communication gap between hospitals and the communities they serve. Patel & Patel (2022) emphasize the importance of enhancing marketing and communication efforts within hospitals to achieve service excellence. Promotion in healthcare is a form of marketing communication aimed at disseminating accurate information, shaping positive perceptions, and encouraging patients to utilize and remain loyal to the services offered. By adopting strategic promotional activities, healthcare providers can strengthen their brand image, improve patient engagement, and ultimately increase revisit intentions.

Conceptual Framework

Patient satisfaction will mediate patient repeat visits if the marketing mix 4P research concept model is as follows.

Figure 2. Research Concept Model

III. METHODOLOGY

The subjects of this study were all outpatients of St. Elisabeth Hospital Bekasi during the period from February to March 2025. The focus of the research was on repeat visits by patients, influenced by product quality and promotional activities, with patient satisfaction serving as a mediating variable. The study population comprised all outpatients of the hospital within the specified timeframe. A purposive sampling technique was employed, wherein participants were selected based on specific predetermined criteria. The total number of respondents was 160, determined using the formula proposed by Hair et al. (2020), which is suitable for studies involving unknown population sizes. Data collection was carried out through the distribution of questionnaires, consisting of written statements delivered directly to the respondents for them to respond to or approve. Each item in the questionnaire utilized a five-point Likert scale, enabling respondents to express their degree of agreement with each statement provided. Data analysis was conducted using the regression method with the Partial Least Squares - Structural Equation Modeling (PLS-SEM) approach. The PLS-SEM method was chosen due to its logical framework and its strength in confirmation, explanation, and prediction capabilities (Hair et al., 2020). The path model in PLS-SEM comprises two components: the structural model (inner model) and the measurement model (outer model). The inner model represents the relationships among constructs (depicted by circles or ovals), whereas the outer model represents the relationships between constructs and their indicators (depicted by rectangles).

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Outer Model Analysis

Validity Test

The tests conducted on the outer model analysis in this study used convergent validity, discriminant validity, composite reliability, and Cronbach's Alpha. For the validity test, an indicator is declared valid if the loading factor measurement is above 0.60 so that if there is a loading factor below 0.60 it will be dropped from the model (Hair et al, 2019).

Table 2. Outer Loading

	Outer loading
KKU1 ← Revisit Decision	0.788
KKU2 ← Revisit Decision	0.835
KKU3 ← Revisit Decision	0.851
KP1 ← Patient Satisfaction	0.832
KP2 ← Patient Satisfaction	0.900
KP3 ← Patient Satisfaction	0.882
KP4 ← Patient Satisfaction	0.910
KPR1 ← Product Quality	0.811
KPR2 ← Product Quality	0.738
KPR3 ← Product Quality	0.779
KPR4 ← Product Quality	0.840
KPR5 ← Product Quality	0.878
P1 ← Promotion	0.828
P2 ← Promotion	0.876
P3 ← Promotion	0.811
P4 ← Promotion	0.845

It is known that all variable items are valid. This is because the loading factor value is above 0.60 (Hair et al, 2019). In addition to the loading factor value, to analyze the validity of research data, the Average Variance Extracted (AVE) value can be used. The following are the results of the validity test using the AVE value.

Table 3. AVE Test Results

	Average variance extracted (AVE)
Patient Satisfaction	0.777
Revisit Decision	0.681
Product Quality	0.657
Promotion	0.706

It is known that all research variables are valid. This is because the AVE value is above the provision of 0.50 (Hair et al, 2019).

Discriminant Validity

In the Fornell-Lacker Criterion, discriminant validity is carried out by comparing the correlation between variables with AVE on a variable. A good discriminant validity measurement model if the AVE on the variable itself is greater than the correlation between other variables (Hair et al, 2019). The overall AVE value can be seen in the following table.

Table 4. Fornell Lacker

	Patient Satisfaction	Revisit Decision	Product Quality	Promotion
Patient Satisfaction	0.882			
Revisit Decision	0.752	0.825		
Product Quality	0.580	0.687	0.810	
Promotion	0.692	0.725	0.632	0.840

It can be seen that the correlation value of this variable is greater than the correlation of other variables, therefore it can be concluded that all variables are valid for use.

In addition to the fornell lacker test, discriminant validity can also be tested based on the cross-loading value. An indicator is declared to meet discriminant validity if the cross-loading value of the dimension on its variable is the largest compared to other variables (Hair et al, 2019). The following are the results of the cross-loading value.

Table 5. Cross Loading Value Results

	Patient Satisfaction	Revisit Decision	Product Quality	Promotion
KKU1	0.603	0.788	0.495	0,513
KKU2	0,640	0,835	0,580	0,589
KKU3	0,619	0,851	0,619	0,683
KP1	0,832	0,570	0,426	0,560
KP2	0,900	0,671	0,517	0,662
KP3	0,882	0,695	0,529	0,583
KP4	0,910	0,705	0,564	0,632
KPR1	0,440	0,524	0,811	0,487
KPR2	0,278	0,487	0,738	0,424
KPR3	0,456	0,516	0,779	0,438
KPR4	0,547	0,603	0,840	0,565
KPR5	0,570	0,634	0,878	0,612
P1	0,590	0,696	0,545	0,828

P2	0,594	0,626	0.598	0.876
P3	0.568	0.536	0.465	0.811
P4	0.572	0.565	0.506	0.845

It can be seen that the correlation value of the indicators on this variable is greater than the correlation on other variables, therefore it is concluded that all variables are valid for use.

Reliability Test

Reliability Test in PLS can use 2 methods, namely Cronbach's alpha and Composite reliability. The following are the results of the research reliability test.

Table 6. Composite Reliability

	Composite reliability (rho_c)	Cronbach's alpha
Patient Satisfaction	0.933	0.904
Revisit Decision	0.865	0.765
Product Quality	0.905	0.870
Promotion	0.906	0.861

All constructs in the study were declared Reliable because the Composite Reliability value for all constructs was above 0.70 (Hair et al, 2019). Then, all constructs in the study were also declared Reliable because the Cronbach's Alpha value for all constructs was above 0.60.

Inner Model Analysis

After the estimated model meets the Outer Model criteria, the researcher then tests the Structural Model (Inner Model). The following are the R-Square (R²) values for the research constructs:

Table 7. Determination Coefficient Test

	R-square	R-square adjusted
Patient Satisfaction	0.513	0.507
Revisit Decision	0.692	0.686

It can be seen that the Adjusted R-Square value for the patient satisfaction variable is 0.507. This means that the model has a strong level of goodness-fit model. This also means that the variability of patient satisfaction can be explained by the independent variable by 50.7%. The Adjusted R-Square value for the revisit decision variable is 0.686. This means that the model has a strong level of goodness-fit model. This also means that the variability of the revisit decision can be explained by the independent variable by 68.6%.

Hypothesis Testing

Table 8. Direct Influence Hypothesis Test

	Original sample (O)	T statistics (O/STDEV)	P Values
Product Quality → Revisit Decision	0.286	2,672	0.008
Promotion → Revisit Decision	0.268	3,266	0.001
Patient Satisfaction → Revisit Decision	0.401	4,365	0,000
Product Quality → Patient Satisfaction	0.238	2,451	0.014
Promotion → Patient Satisfaction	0.542	6,402	0,000

The results of the analysis show that product quality has a positive and significant effect on patient revisit decisions. This is indicated by the original sample estimate value of 0.286 with a t-statistic value of 2.672, which is greater than the critical limit of 1.96 (Ghozali, 2014). Thus, Hypothesis H1 is declared accepted.

Furthermore, promotion is also proven to have a positive and significant effect on patient revisit decisions. The original sample estimate value for this relationship is 0.268 with a t-statistic of 3.266 (>1.96), so Hypothesis H2 in this study is accepted.

The variable of patient satisfaction on the decision to revisit shows a positive and significant influence, with an original sample estimate value of 0.401 and a t-statistic of 4.365, which also exceeds the critical value of 1.96. With these results, Hypothesis H3 is declared accepted.

In addition, product quality has been proven to have a positive and significant effect on patient satisfaction, with an original sample estimate value of 0.238 and a t-statistic of 2.451 (>1.96). Therefore, Hypothesis H4 in this study is declared accepted.

Finally, promotion was found to have a positive and significant effect on patient satisfaction. The results of the analysis showed an original sample estimate value of 0.542 with a t-statistic of 6.402, which far exceeded the critical limit of 1.96. Based on these results, Hypothesis H5 is declared accepted.

Table 9. Hypothesis Test of Indirect Influence

	Original sample (O)	T statistics ((O/STDEV))	P values
Product Quality → Patient Satisfaction → Revisit Decision	0.095	3,085	0.006
Promotion → Patient Satisfaction → Revisit Decision	0.217	3,975	0,000

Further analysis results show that product quality has a positive and significant effect on the decision to revisit through patient satisfaction as a mediating variable. This is indicated by the original sample estimate value of 0.095 with a t-statistic value of 3.085, which is greater than the critical value of 1.96 (Ghozali, 2014). Based on these results, Hypothesis H6 is declared accepted.

Furthermore, promotion is also proven to have a positive and significant effect on the decision to revisit through patient satisfaction. The analysis produces an original sample estimate value of 0.217 with a t-statistic of 3.975 (> 1.96), which indicates the significance of the relationship. Thus, Hypothesis H7 in this study is declared accepted.

Discussion

This study shows that product quality has a positive effect on revisit decisions. This is proven through analysis in the table showing the original sample estimate value of 0.286 with a t-statistic of 2.672 (> 1.96) based on Ghozali (2014), so it can be concluded that product quality has a significant effect on revisit decisions. This finding is consistent with research conducted by Utami, Saparso, & Wahyoedi (2023) which states that product quality plays an important role in shaping customer loyalty through revisit decisions, especially in the context of hospital services.

In addition, promotion has also been shown to have a positive effect on repeat visit decisions. Based on the analysis results, the original sample estimate value of 0.268 with a t-statistic of 3.266 (>1.96) indicates that effective promotion can increase the tendency of patients to make repeat visits. This phenomenon is in line with the findings of Sirajuddin, Shazrina, & Senathirajah (2023) which stated that promotion, along with location factors, has a major impact on consumer repeat purchase behavior in the Malaysian cosmetics market.

Patient satisfaction was also found to have a positive effect on the decision to revisit, as seen from the original sample estimate value of 0.401 and the t-statistic of 4.365 (>1.96). This emphasizes the importance of service efforts that focus on creating positive experiences, which will ultimately strengthen customer trust and loyalty. This finding is supported by research by Lepianda, Gunardi, & Fushen (2024) which proves that patient satisfaction significantly influences loyalty in the beauty clinic service sector.

Furthermore, product quality has been shown to have a positive effect on patient satisfaction with an original sample estimate value of 0.238 and a t-statistic of 2.451 (>1.96). This shows that good product quality can increase patient satisfaction levels, in accordance with the findings of Larasati et al. (2023) who emphasized the importance of service quality and complaint handling in building patient satisfaction.

Promotion also showed a positive effect on patient satisfaction with an original sample estimate value of 0.542 and a t-statistic of 6.402 (>1.96), which means that effective promotion not only increases patient awareness of products or services but also strengthens their satisfaction with the decisions taken. This finding is in line with the research of Paradilla & Janna (2022) which found that the marketing mix, including promotion, has a significant effect on patient loyalty through satisfaction at Stella Maris Hospital Makassar.

This study also proves the mediation effect of patient satisfaction in the relationship between product quality and revisit decisions. The results of the analysis show that product quality has a positive effect on revisit decisions through patient satisfaction, with an original sample estimate value of 0.095 and a t-statistic of 3.085 (>1.96). This indicates that patient satisfaction strengthens the relationship between product quality and revisit decisions (Utami et al., 2023).

Similarly, promotion has a positive effect on revisit decisions through patient satisfaction, with an original sample estimate value of 0.217 and a t-statistic of 3.975 (>1.96). These results indicate that effective promotion can increase patient satisfaction, which in turn encourages them to make repeat visits. This finding is in line with the research of Pinyo et al. (2018) which proves that satisfaction with the marketing mix, including promotion, has an impact on consumer loyalty in the context of the Joox application.

V. CONCLUSION AND SUGGESTIONS

Based on the results of the discussion and analysis that have been carried out, it can be concluded that product quality and promotion have a positive influence on patient satisfaction and the decision to make a repeat visit. Patient satisfaction has also been shown to have a direct influence on the decision to make a repeat visit, while also acting as a mediating variable between product quality and promotion on the decision to make a repeat visit. From the results of the questionnaire analysis, it is known that the most prominent aspect in shaping patient satisfaction is the hospital service system. In the product quality variable, the empathy indicator is the most important, reflecting the sincere and personal attention given to patients and a deep understanding of individual needs. Meanwhile, in the promotion variable, promotional media is the most influential element in attracting patient interest. As for the variable of the decision to make a repeat visit, positive reviews by patients are the dominant indicator, indicating satisfaction that encourages the willingness to use hospital services again. These findings underline the importance of improving service quality, effective promotional approaches, and a deep understanding of patient needs in increasing their loyalty to the hospital.

Based on the research results, there are several suggestions that are expected to be useful for various parties. Academically, further research is suggested to use a larger and more varied number of respondents, for example based on education and income, so that the results are more representative of real conditions. Further researchers are also expected to use this study as a reference, focusing on non-profit hospitals outside Bekasi City. For the hospital, the questionnaire results show the importance of improving service quality indicators, including physical facilities, reliability, responsiveness, and service guarantees. In terms of promotion, hospitals need to pay attention to messages, time, and frequency of promotions to be more effective. Regarding patient satisfaction, attention needs to be given to access, quality, and service processes. Meanwhile, to encourage repeat visits, hospitals need to build patients' desire to return and provide recommendations. St. Elisabeth Hospital is also advised to conduct further research related to patient and family experiences in order to understand customer expectations in more depth. A planned service marketing strategy needs to be prepared immediately to improve the hospital's competitiveness and image. Finally, the best service both before and after the service needs to be improved to maintain patient loyalty.

REFERENCES

1. Abbasi-Moghaddam, M. A., Zarei, E., Bagherzadeh, R., Dargahi, H., & Farrokhi, P. (2019). Evaluation of service quality from patients' viewpoint. *BMC health services research*, 19(1), 170. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12913-019-3998-0>
2. Al-Damen, R. (2017) Health Care Service Quality and Its Impact on Patient Satisfaction "Case of Al-Bashir Hospital". *International Journal of Business and Management*, 12, 136-152. <https://doi.org/10.5539/ijbm.v12n9p136>

3. Asnawi, A. A., Awang, Z., Afthanorhan, A., Mohamad, M., & Karim, F. (2019). The influence of hospital image and service quality on patients' satisfaction and loyalty. *Management Science Letters*, 9(6), 911–920. <https://doi.org/10.5267/j.msl.2019.2.011>
4. Elliott, R. A., Camacho, E., Jankovic, D., Sculpher, M. J., & Faria, R. (2021). Economic analysis of the prevalence and clinical and economic burden of medication error in England. *BMJ quality & safety*, 30(2), 96–105. <https://doi.org/10.1136/bmjqs-2019-010206>
5. Fadlilah, I. N., & Listyorini, S. (2022). Pengaruh kualitas pelayanan, fasilitas, dan harga terhadap kepuasan pasien. *Jurnal Ilmu Administrasi Bisnis*, 11(1). Universitas Diponegoro Semarang. <https://doi.org/10.14710/jiab.2022.33542>
6. Ghozali, I. (2021). *Aplikasi Analisis Multivariete Dengan Program IBM SPSS 26*. Edisi 10. Semarang: Badan Penerbit Universitas Diponegoro.
7. Haryanto, E., Hadiati, A., & Purwanti, L. S. (2019). Kepuasan Pasien Berdasarkan Waktu Tunggu Pelayanan di Puskesmas Ibrahim Adjie Kota Bandung. *Jurnal Ilmiah JKA (Jurnal Kesehatan Aeromedika)*, 5(2):25-35. DOI: 10.58550/jka.v5i2.83
8. Joe F. Hair, Matt C. Howard, & Christian Nitzl. (2020). Assessing measurement model quality in PLS-SEM using confirmatory composite analysis. *Journal of Business Research*, Volume 109, Pages 101-110, ISSN 0148-2963. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jbusres.2019.11.069>
9. Kartika, Mira Gayarti, Kurniawati, Ony. (2025). Pengaruh Kualitas Produk, Kualitas Pelayanan, dan Tarif terhadap Kepuasan Pasien RSUD dr. Mohamad Soewandhie Surabaya. *Jurnal Simki Economic* 8(1). <https://doi.org/10.29407/jse.v8i1.1068>
10. Kiran, M. Patel., & Kateryna, Metersky. (2022). Reflective Practice in Nursing: A Concept Analysis. *International Journal of Nursing Knowledge*, Vol. 33(3), Pp. 180 – 187.
11. Lende, S., yadi, S., & Zaharuddin. (2025). Dampak Sistem Informasi Manajemen, Kualitas Pelayanan, dan Kepuasan Pasien terhadap Loyalitas Pasien di Rumah Sakit XYZ. *Arus Jurnal Sosial Dan Humaniora*, 5(1), 223–231. <https://doi.org/10.57250/ajsh.v5i1.1040>
12. Lepianda, J., Gunardi, W. D., & Fushen. (2024). The Effect of Service Quality and Patient Satisfaction on Patient Loyalty Mediated by Patient Trust at Byor Skin Clinic. (2024). *Maneggio*, 1(4), 9-29.
13. Mellenia, J., Ardi, A., & Wuisan, D. S. S. (2025). Pengaruh Kualitas Pelayanan, Komunikasi, Kepercayaan Merek, Dan Kepercayaan Pasien Kepada Dokter Terhadap Loyalitas Pasien Dimediasi Dengan Kepuasan Pasien Di Rumah Sakit Hermina Arcamanik. *Prepotif: Jurnal Kesehatan Masyarakat*, 9(1), 455–463. <https://doi.org/10.31004/prepotif.v9i1.40166>
14. Mene Paradilla, & Nur Miftahul Janna. (2023). Pengaruh Marketing Mix dan Patient Experience Melalui Kepuasan Terhadap Loyalitas Pasien Umum di Instalasi Rawat Inap Rumah Sakit Stella Maris Makassar Tahun 2022. *INSOLOGI: Jurnal Sains Dan Teknologi*, 2(4), 811–823. <https://doi.org/10.55123/insologi.v2i4.2503>
15. Pinyo, W., & Worapishet, T. (2018, June). The relationship between customer loyalty and marketing mix satisfaction of music streaming service. In *Proceedings of International Academic Conferences* (No. 7208910). International Institute of Social and Economic Sciences.
16. Putri Utami, R., & Wahyoedi, S. (2023). Analisis Kualitas Produk, Pelayanan Dan Citra Merek Terhadap Loyalitas Yang Di Mediasi Oleh Kepuasan Pelanggan Pada Klinik Erha Jakarta Selatan Analysis of Product Quality, Service and Brand Image on Loyalty Mediated By Customer Satisfaction At the Erha C. *Journal of Social and Economics Research*, 5(2), 1886–1899. <https://idm.or.id/JSER/ind>
17. Richter, J. P., & Muhlestein, D. B. (2017). Patient experience and hospital profitability. *Health Care Management Review*, 42(3), 247–257. <https://doi.org/10.1097/hmr.000000000000105>
18. Salsabila, T. A., Purwanda, E., & Yuliaty, F. (2024). Kualitas Pelayanan Sebagai Faktor Penentu Kepuasan Dan Loyalitas Pasien Di Rumah Sakit. *Ekoma*, 4(1), 1105–1120. <http://dx.doi.org/10.56799/ekoma.v4i1.5359>
19. Sirajuddin, R. S. B., Senathirajah, A. R. B. S., Haque, R., & Isa, A. M. M. (2023). Marketing Mix Influence on Consumer Buying Behavior: A Case Study on the Cosmetics Industry. *International Journal of Professional Business Review*, 8(5), e01499. <https://doi.org/10.26668/businessreview/2023.v8i5.1499>
20. Suaeb, M. I. (2023). Pengaruh Kualitas Layanan dan Harga terhadap Kepuasan Pasien. *Paradoks: Jurnal Ilmu Ekonomi*, 6(3), 218–231. <https://jurnal.feb-umi.id/index.php/PARADOKS/article/view/683>

21. Sulisty A., & Gumilar A. (2019). Studi Citra Rumah Sakit Dan Kualitas Pelayanan Terhadap Loyalitas Pelanggan Melalui Kepuasan Pelanggan Pada Rumah Sakit Awal Bros Tangerang. *JMB Jurnal Manajemen dan Bisnis*, 8(2).
22. Tjiptono, F. (2016). *Service, Quality & Satisfaction*. Yogyakarta: Andi.
23. Yuliantine, T., Indasah, I., & Siyoto, S. (2018). Analysis of marketing mix characteristics of marketing factor 7P (Product, Price, Place, Promotion, People, Process, Physical Building) to patient satisfaction of inpatient patient hospital Muhammadiyah Ahmad Dahlan Kediri City. *Journal for Quality in Public Health*, 1(2), 50-57.

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